

An inequality on Fischer-type Determinant for accretive-dissipative matrices

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Abstract In this paper, we study the Fischer-type determinant inequality for accretive-dissipative matrix. Inspired by Ikramov and Lin, as a result, a new inequality about Fischer-type determinant inequality of accretive-dissipative matrix is given, at the same time, we extend the corresponding result.

Keywords Fischer-type Determinant; accretive-dissipative matrix; inequality

1. Introduction

Let I_n be an $n \times n$ unit matrix, $M^{m \times n}$ be the set of $m \times n$ complex matrices, if A be a $n \times n$ matrix, denote the eigenvalues of A by $\lambda_i(A)$, the conjugate transpose of A by A^H , A is called positive semi-definite matrix if A be a Herimite matrix and $\lambda_i(A) > 0$. For any $A \in M^{n \times n}$, the following decomposition is called the Herimite decomposition of A , if A can be uniquely decomposed into:

$$A = B + iC. \quad (1.1)$$

where

$$B = \frac{A + A^H}{2}, \quad C = \frac{A - A^H}{2i},$$

and B, C are Herimite matrices. B, C are called the real part and the imaginary part of A respectively. For simplicity, (1.1) is always expressed in blocks as

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1.2)$$

say $k, l (k > 0, l > 0, k + l = n)$ the order of A_{11} and A_{22} , respectively, and let $m = \min\{k, l\}$. Since B, C are Herimite matrices, then

$$B_{12} = B_{21}^H, \quad C_{12} = C_{21}^H.$$

If $B = I_n$ in (1.1), then A is called Buckley matrix. If B in (1.1) is a positive semi-definite matrix, then A is called accretive matrix. If C in (1.1) is a positive semi-definite matrix, then A is called dissipative matrix. If B, C in (1.1) are positive semi-definite matrices, then A is called accretive-dissipative matrix. In this definition, A is a dissipative matrix if and only if $-iA$ is a accretive matrix.

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{pmatrix} \in M^{n \times n}$, if A_{11} is invertible, then the Schur complement of A_{11} in A is denoted by

$A / A_{11} := A_{22} - A_{21}A_{11}^{-1}A_{12}$. For a nonsingular matrix A , the condition number of A is denoted by

$$\kappa(A) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{\max}(A^H A)}{\lambda_{\min}(A^H A)}}$$

which is the ratio of the largest and the smallest singular value of A .

In 1985, Horn and Johnson ([1], p478) gave the famous Fischer-type determinantal inequality

$$|\det A| \leq |\det A_{11}| |\det A_{22}|. \tag{1.3}$$

In 2004, Ikramov [2] first proved the determinantal inequality of accretive-dissipative matrix

$$|\det A| \leq 3^m |\det A_{11}| |\det A_{22}|. \tag{1.4}$$

In 2013, if $A \in M^{n \times n}$ is accretive-dissipative, Lin [3] got the result

$$|\det A| \leq 2^{\frac{3}{2}m} |\det A_{11}| |\det A_{22}|. \tag{1.5}$$

Fu and He [4] got a stronger result than (1.5):

$$|\det A| \leq 2^{\frac{1}{2}m} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\kappa}{1+\kappa} \right)^2 \right)^m |\det A_{11}| |\det A_{22}|. \tag{1.6}$$

where $\kappa = \max\{\kappa(A), \kappa(B)\}$.

The purpose of this paper is to use the existing conclusions to present a new inequality on Fischer-type Determinant for accretive-dissipative matrix, and extend the result of Fu and He.

2. Main Result

In this section, we begin with the following lemmas.

Lemma 2.1^[5] Let $A \in M^{n \times n}$ be accretive-dissipative as in (1.2), then A / A_{11} is also accretive –dissipative.

Lemma 2.2^[2] Let $A \in M^{n \times n}$ be accretive-dissipative as in (1.2), then

$$A^{-1} = E - iF,$$

where

$$E = (B + CB^{-1}C)^{-1}, \quad F = (C + BC^{-1}B)^{-1}.$$

Lemma 2.3^[2] Let $A = I_n + iC$ be Buckley matrix, then

$$A^{-1} = E + iF, \quad E = (I_n + C^2)^{-1}, \quad F = -(C + C^{-1})^{-1} = -C(I_n + C^2)^{-1}.$$

Lemma 2.4^[5] Let $A \in M^{n \times n}$ be Herimite matrix and $B > 0$, then

$$B + CB^{-1}C \geq 2C.$$

Lemma 2.5^[3] Let $B, C \in M^{n \times n}$ be positive semi-definite, then

$$|\det(B + iC)| \leq \det(B + C) \leq 2^{\frac{n}{2}} |\det(B + iC)|.$$

Lemma 2.6^[6] Let $A \in M^{n \times n}$ be positive definite, then

$$A_{12}A_{22}^{-1}A_{21} \leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_n}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_n} \right)^2 A_{11},$$

where λ_1 and λ_n are the maximum eigenvalue and minimum eigenvalue of A , respectively.

Now, we are ready to give our result.

Theorem 1 Let $A \in M^{n \times n}$ be accretive-dissipative as in (1.1), then

$$|\det A| \leq (2x^2 + 2y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}m} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\kappa}{1+\kappa} \right)^2 \right)^m |\det A_{11}| \left| \det \left(\frac{B_{22}}{x} + i \frac{C_{22}}{y} \right) \right|. \quad (2.1)$$

where $\kappa = \max\{\kappa(B), \kappa(C)\}$ and $x, y \in R$ are positive.

Proof. By Lemmas 2.1-2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A / A_{11} &= A_{22} - A_{21}A_{11}^{-1}A_{12} \\ &= B_{22} + iC_{22} - (B_{12}^H + iC_{12}^H)(B_{11} + iC_{11})^{-1}(B_{12} + iC_{12}) \\ &= B_{22} + iC_{22} - (B_{12}^H + iC_{12}^H)(E_k - iF_k)(B_{12} + iC_{12}). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously,

$$E_k = (B_{11} + C_{11}B_{11}^{-1}C_{11})^{-1}, \quad F_k = (C_{11} + B_{11}C_{11}^{-1}B_{11})^{-1},$$

where E_k and F_k are positive definite.

By Lemma 2.4, and the monotonicity of invertible operator inverse, we obtain

$$E_k \leq \frac{1}{2}C_{11}^{-1}, \quad F_k \leq \frac{1}{2}B_{11}^{-1}. \quad (2.2)$$

Let $A / A_{11} = R + iS$, $R = R^H$, $S = S^H$, by lemma 2.1, R and S are positive definite, by computation, we get

$$\begin{aligned} R &= B_{22} - B_{12}^H E_k B_{12} + C_{12}^H E_k C_{12} - B_{12}^H F_k C_{12} - C_{12}^H F_k B_{12}, \\ S &= C_{22} + B_{12}^H F_k B_{12} - C_{12}^H F_k C_{12} - C_{12}^H E_k B_{12} - B_{12}^H E_k C_{12}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$(B_{12}^H \pm C_{12}^H)F_k(B_{12} \pm C_{12}) \geq 0, \quad (B_{12}^H \pm C_{12}^H)E_k(B_{12} \pm C_{12}) \geq 0,$$

it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \pm(B_{12}^H F_k C_{12} + C_{12}^H F_k B_{12}) &\leq B_{12}^H F_k B_{12} + C_{12}^H F_k C_{12}, \\ \pm(C_{12}^H E_k B_{12} + B_{12}^H E_k C_{12}) &\leq B_{12}^H E_k B_{12} + C_{12}^H E_k C_{12}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$R + S \leq B_{22} + 2B_{12}^H F_k B_{12} + C_{22} + 2C_{12}^H E_k C_{12}. \quad (2.3)$$

Recall B, C are positive definite, by lemma 2.6, we have

$$B_{12}B_{22}^{-1}B_{12}^H \leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_n}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_n} \right)^2 B_{11}, \quad C_{12}C_{22}^{-1}C_{12}^H \leq \left(\frac{\lambda'_1 - \lambda'_n}{\lambda'_1 + \lambda'_n} \right)^2 C_{11}. \quad (2.4)$$

where λ_1 and λ_n (λ'_1 and λ'_n) are the maximum eigenvalue and minimum eigenvalue of B (C).

Then

$$B_{12}^H B_{11}^{-1} B_{12} \leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_n}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_n} \right)^2 B_{22}, \quad C_{12}^H C_{11}^{-1} C_{12} \leq \left(\frac{\lambda'_1 - \lambda'_n}{\lambda'_1 + \lambda'_n} \right)^2 C_{22}. \quad (2.5)$$

Let $f(z) = \left(\frac{z-1}{z+1} \right)^m$ ($m \geq 1$), $f(z)$ is increasing on $[1, \infty)$. In general, we let $m = l$,

$\lambda_j, j = 1, \dots, n$ are the eigenvalues of $B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_{22} B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, and $B_{22}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is the unique positive definite square root of B_{22} , then, we get

$$|1 + i\lambda_j| \leq |1 + \lambda_j| \leq \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \left| \frac{1}{x} + i \frac{\lambda_j}{y} \right|. \quad (2.6)$$

Set

$$\rho = 2^{\frac{1}{2}m} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\kappa}{1+\kappa} \right)^2 \right)^m,$$

by lemma 2.5 and (2.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \det \frac{A}{A_{11}} \right| &= |\det R + iS| \leq \det(R + S) \leq \det(B_{22} + 2B_{12}^H F_k B_{12} + C_{22} + 2C_{12}^H E_k C_{12}) \\ &\leq \det(B_{22} + B_{12}^H B_{11}^{-1} B_{12} + C_{22} + C_{12}^H C_{11}^{-1} C_{12}) \\ &\leq \det \left(B_{22} + C_{22} + \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_n}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_n} \right)^2 B_{22} + \left(\frac{\lambda'_1 - \lambda'_n}{\lambda'_1 + \lambda'_n} \right)^2 C_{22} \right) \\ &= \det \left(B_{22} + C_{22} + \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - 1}{\lambda_1 + 1} \right)^2 B_{22} + \left(\frac{\lambda'_1 - 1}{\lambda'_1 + 1} \right)^2 C_{22} \right) \\ &\leq \left(1 + \left(\frac{\kappa - 1}{\kappa + 1} \right)^2 \right)^m \det(B_{22} + C_{22}) \leq \rho |\det(B_{22} + iC_{22})| \leq \rho |\det(B_{22} + C_{22})| \\ &= \rho \left| \det B_{22}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(I + B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_{22} B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) B_{22}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right| \\ &= \rho \left| \det B_{22}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right| \left| \det B_{22}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right| \left| \det \left(I + B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_{22} B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right| \\ &= \rho |\det B_{22}| \prod_{j=1}^m |1 + \lambda_j| \\ &\leq \rho |\det B_{22}| \prod_{j=1}^m \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \left| \frac{1}{x} + i \frac{\lambda_j}{y} \right| \\ &= \rho (x^2 + y^2)^{\frac{m}{2}} |\det B_{22}| \left| \det \left(\frac{I}{x} + \frac{i}{y} B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_{22} B_{22}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right| \\ &= \rho (x^2 + y^2)^{\frac{m}{2}} \left| \det \left(\frac{B_{22}}{x} + i \frac{C_{22}}{y} \right) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\kappa = \max \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_n}, \frac{\lambda'_1}{\lambda'_n} \right) \geq 1,$$

it is the maximum condition number of B, C . Since

$$|\det A| = |\det A_{11}| \left| \det \frac{A}{A_{11}} \right|,$$

then

$$|\det A| \leq (2x^2 + 2y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}m} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\kappa}{1+\kappa} \right)^2 \right)^m |\det A_{11}| \left| \det \begin{pmatrix} B_{22} + i \frac{C_{22}}{y} \\ x \end{pmatrix} \right|.$$

Therefore, we complete Theorem 1.

Remark 1 It is clear that inequality (2.1) is an extension of inequality (1.6).

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